

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D5.3

Design, implementation and deployment of Research Object services – phase II

Grant agreement number	101017501
Start date of the project	Reliance
Duration of the project	30 months
Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Coordinator	PSNC

Due date of delivery	30/09/2022
Actual date of delivery	17/10/2022
Work package	WP5
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Responsible	PSNC
Reviewer	ESI
Version	1.0

This project has received funding from the European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017501

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History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Authors	Organization
1.1	28/09/2022	Section 4	Esteban González	UPM
1.2	29/09/2022	Executive summary	Raul Palma	PSNC
1.3	30/09/2022	Sections 1-3 update	Raul Palma	PSNC
1.4	3/10/2022	Section 5 update	Raul Palma	PSNC
1.5	4/10/2022	Section 6-7 updates	Raul Palma	PSNC
1.6	5/10/2022	Section 7 update, bibliography	Raul Palma	PSNC
1.7	6/10/2022	Final formatting	Raul Palma	PSNC

Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management platform
API	Application Programming Interface
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
IAM	Identity and Access Management
Minim	Minimum information Model
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PyPI	Python Package Index
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RO	Research Object

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the second version of the tools and services for Research Objects (ROs) management, resulting from the WP5 tasks. In particular, such tools and services include the latest release of ROHub platform, the services for FAIR assessment and quality assessment of Research Objects and their integration in ROHub, the extended Research Objects evolution mechanism adapted to EOSC scenarios and their implemented in ROHub, the integration of services from WP3 (text mining) and WP4 (data cubes) in ROHub, the integration of other external EOSC services in ROHub, and the latest user interfaces of ROHub.

An important input for this deliverable and for the work carried out in the implementation of WP5 services is the vocabulary specification that is used in RELIANCE for the representation of the Research Objects, which has been implemented as an RO-crate profile, and which is described in D5.1. A key characteristic of the proposed RO specification is regarding the data-cube centric Research Object, as a fundamental differentiating principle of the Earth Science communities that are supported by RELIANCE. As described in D4.1, Data Cubes are becoming a reference service to provide a data access infrastructure and a reference set of tools for geospatial data management, mostly related to the access and exploitation of large collections of multi-temporal, multi-resolution satellite imagery at national/international scale. RELIANCE leverages data cubes to provide earth scientists with an efficient and scalable structured data access and discovery. Scientists are able to aggregate and describe data cubes in their Research Objects, and connect them with related resources (e.g., products generated, methods used for processing, publications generated, infrastructures used, etc.), in line with FAIR and open science principles.

This document is the second version describing the design, implementation and deployment of Research Object services. This is an updated version of deliverable D5.2, therefore it includes content from D5.2 regarding previous results, plus the new content describing the results during this second period. In particular, the sections content is as follows:

- Section 1 – executive summary has been updated to reflect latest results
- Section 2 – Introduction has been updated to reflect latest results
- Section 3 – RO crate profile has not been updated (finalized in previous release)
- Section 4 – completely new and updated content. This includes the approach for measuring RO FAIRness assessment and the FAIROs service that has been recently developed.
- Section 5 – updated content, and in a new section has been introduced to describe the new checklist generation tool, which enables the creation and customization of checklists using a simplified template.
- Section 6 – updated content, particularly regarding the use and exploitation of B2Drop EOSC services to store RO resources.
- Section 7 – major updated content describing the latest integrations in ROHub, including several EOSC services and the latest results from WP3 and WP4. This section has been extensively extended.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope

RELIANCE is extending the EOSC service offering with a set of industry-strong, innovative, interconnected services for the open, efficient, and cross-disciplinary management of the research lifecycle, adopting a holistic approach to address research activities in accordance with FAIR and Open Science principles. The core technology behind RELIANCE services is Research Objects, as the overarching information artefact to manage the research activities. Research Objects, aka FAIR digital objects, are semantically rich aggregations of data, methods and people in scientific

investigations supporting the implementation of FAIR guiding principles and the systemic change of science practices to Open Science. They describe and associate all of this content together in a machine-readable mechanism so that it can be more easily shared and exchanged. Research Objects have been successfully applied by early adopters in Earth Science (see [1]), and in RELIANCE they are being further demonstrated in different multidisciplinary and vertical use cases in Earth Science. To that end, Research Objects in RELIANCE rely on Data Cubes for an efficient and scalable structured data access and discovery (see D4.2), as well as text mining services that extract machine-readable metadata from scholarly communications and Data Cube descriptions (see D3.2), among others, providing researchers with means to discover scientific information at scale and structure their own research.

In RELIANCE, the core Research Object services are provided by the ROHub platform, while Data Cubes services are provided by the ADAM platform. The latest version of ADAM interfaces is described in detail in deliverable D4.4. Similarly, the text mining services are provided by expert.ai, and the latest release of these services are described in detail in D3.2 and D3.3 (delivered alongside this deliverable).

Both of these services and technologies are being interconnected in ROHub to allow seamless access from different interfaces, using Research Objects as the main connecting point. Data Cubes can be linked in the Research Object as first-class entities but also described with a rich set of metadata (e.g., how it was generated or used). The text mining & enrichment services, which include the production-ready and extended analytic services are integrated or being integrated in ROHub as added value services. The production services comprise i) the enrichment, ii) the search and iii) the recommendation services, with the related collaboration spheres GUI (described in D3.2 and D3.3), which aim to increase the findability and reuse of Research Objects by generating structured metadata from the Research Object and its textual content. The new extended analytic services have been recently implemented (as described in D3.3), and include: i) the challenge and solution extraction service, ii) the question generation service, iii) the claim analysis service, iv) the novelty scoring service and the RELISH (RELIANCE Dashboard). ROHub integrates the latest release of the production services, whereas the integration of the extended analytics services is just starting. Additionally, ROHub integrates already other Research Objects added value services, including the i) checklist service to assess the Research Object quality (completeness) based on community requirements, ii) a PDF service to generate a paper view of the Research Object in PDF format, while iii) the FAIRness assessment service (recently released) and iv) the quality monitoring service are currently under integration.

All of the core RELIANCE services have been onboarded in EOSC and, in particular, ROHub integrates and/or reuses several other EOSC services, including: i) EGI check-in for the authentication and identity management; ii) B2Drop as an alternative personal storage of physical resources aggregated in Research Objects; iii) B2Share and iv) Zenodo as an added value service for the publication of Research Objects snapshots/releases; v) OpenAire Research Graph, to enable the discovery of Research Objects and other relevant resources from OpenAire/EOSC explore portal; vi) EGI notebooks to enable users to load and execute their notebooks directly from ROHub and vii) with EGI binder to also reproduce the execution environment.

Based on those integrations, RELIANCE can act as a bridge between various EOSC services, e.g., connecting data used by researchers, including Data Cubes for accessing Copernicus data and other data resources deposited in EOSC services (e.g., B2DROP, B2SHARE), the methods used to process such data (e.g., via EGI Notebooks), and the final results published via scholarly communication services (e.g., Zenodo). Moreover, as part of the RO evolution, different snapshots/releases can be

generated throughout the research lifecycle, so that they can be shared and published via research data platforms like B2SHARE and Zenodo for their long-term preservation and citation.

2.2 Audience

The target audience of this deliverable is manifold. Firstly, this document is intended to serve the RELIANCE Consortium, since it presents the set of services for using and managing Research Objects, which is particularly useful for the current user communities. The document also targets RELIANCE services providers and, more generally, developers of tools and services that may leverage or create Research Objects, as it describes the programmatic interfaces to use/integrate these services with other services. Additionally, this deliverable will be useful for other EOSC-related projects, since it provides a description of the Research Objects services that have been onboarded and made available to other EOSC projects and in general to the EOSC community. Finally, the document is useful for early adopters coming from our existing or new communities, since it provides a reference for them to use the Research Object services and tools.

2.3 Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 3 presents an overview of the RELIANCE RO-crate profile implementation (resulting from D5.1). This section has not been updated from D5.1
- Section 4 presents the results regarding guidelines and tools for FAIR assessment of Research Objects
- Section 5 presents the results regarding the community-driven quality assessment methods and tools.
- Section 6 presents the results regarding the mechanisms for the management of versioning and evolution of Research Objects, and their adaptation to EOSC scenarios.
- Section 7 presents the results regarding the integration and reuse of RELIANCE services and other EOSC services, and the interfaces developed to access Research Object functionalities.

3 RELIANCE RO-crate profile

RO-Crate¹ is a community created to define a lightweight specification for packaging Research Objects. This specification is based on schema.org² annotations in JSON-LD. Schema.org provides a vocabulary to describe structure data on the Internet. Concepts as Organizations, Persons, Digital Objects and Actions can be modeled in a standard vocabulary, as well as their associated metadata. RELIANCE members are part of the ro-crate initiative³ and have contributed to its specification process [2], [3].

The use of this specification reports some advantages:

- All the Research Objects are homogeneous.
- The Research Objects generated can be used by a wider community
- The Research Objects can be manipulated for other tools generated by the community. Some examples can be found here: <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/tools/>

The Research Objects used JSON-LD as format files. JSON-LD is designed to represent linked data on the Internet allowing in our case to express the relations between the different resources of a Research Object. Also, the use of this format facilitates the consumption of Research Objects for other services, it means, gives support to a M2M (Machine to Machine) model.

¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

² <https://schema.org/>

³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/community.html>

The specification selected to describe our Research Objects is 1.1 (the latest version of the specification).

According to RO-Crate, a Research Object has the following structure:

- RO-Crate Metadata file. This file must be written with the format JSON-LD 1.0 and has to be named like ro-crate-metadata.json. This metadata file is generated by the tool ACTION-ASSET (see next section). The resources that compound Research Objects, and relations between them must be described in this document.
- RO-Crate Website. In this case, a human readable version of the Research Object can be attached. In our case, this version is supported by the platform ROHub, where our ROs are shared.
- Payload files and directories. In the context of ACTION, our ROs are not created with the files inside them. All these resources are external, and they are published in repositories like Zenodo, YouTube, SlideShare, etc.

RO-Crate can model a huge variety of different ROs. RELIANCE adds a new type of RO named Data Cube centric Research Object. The definition of Data Cube is still missing, although the Open Geospatial Consortium is working on it. A Data Cube is designed for accessing to large volumes (and variety) of geospatial data. A Data Cube is a multi-dimensional concept and consists of a comprehensive set of functions that describes digital resources (see D4. 1)

The Data Cube services describe both the data structure (e.g., its spatial resolution or temporal dimensions and granularity), to all the available services to exploit discovery, access, view and analytics services. In summary, a Data Cube is a particular view (dataset) of a collection of data filtered by temporal and spatial dimensions.

According to the metadata model proposed for Data Cubes in D4.1, there is a coverage metadata layer in Data Cubes to cover these dimensions. It is composed of the following metadata fields.

- **Simple Geolocation** that represents the shape of the location (point, box and polygon).
- **Spatial coverage**, with additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, coordinate reference system)
- **Temporal coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit)
- **Vertical coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit)

Coming back to RO-Crate, to model places and time, RO-Crate introduces the concept of **Contextual Entities**, which are entities that exist outside the digital sphere, such as locations, people and time. These contextual entities can be associated with data entities like dataset. For that, a data cube can be modeled as follows.

First, the place must be specified. Remember RO-Crate is based on schema.org so the attributes of this vocabulary can be used in our JSON-LD. To use a name of a place, for example Catalina Park, an identifier for the service geonames.org must be provided. This would be an example in RO-Crate:

```
{
  "@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/",
  "@type": "Place",
  "description": "Catalina Park is a disused motor racing venue, located at Katoomba ...",
  "geo": {
```

```

"@id": "#b4168a98-8534-4c6d-a568-64a55157b656"
},
"uri": "https://www.geonames.org/8152662/catalina-park.html",
"name": "Catalina Park"
},

```

Also, an specific location can be expressed with the type `GeoCoordinates`. In this case, the content of the JSON-LD should be:

```

{
"@type": "GeoCoordinates",
"name": "Catalina Park",
"latitude": "43.088521",
"longitude": "-79.072930",
"name": "Latitude: 43.088521 Longitude: -79.072930"
},

```

To represent shapes, RO-Crate has the type `GeoShape` that can model a box, a circle, a line or a polygon.

Once a place is described, it must be linked to a Dataset. Remember that our Data Cubes are datasets at final. For that, we must use the attribute **contentLocation** inside the description of our dataset.

All these elements fulfill the spatial coverage requirements of our Data Cube centric RO, so there is no need to extend or add more elements to the specification of RO-Crate.

In the case of **Time coverage**, we can make use of the attribute **temporalCoverage** in the dataset entity. The values used in this field can be `DateTime` (specific time point) or a textual string indicating a time period (ISO 8601 format). For example, we can use the texts `2020/2021` or `2000 - 2021` to indicate periods of time. With this field, the temporal requirements of our Data Cube model can be covered.

Regarding **Vertical coverage**, both `GeoCoordinates` and `GeoShape` contain a field to describe the elevation of the location. The only missing part respecting the specification of the Data Cube model is the related with the vertical coverage range. A particular elevation can be expressed but not a range of them, it means, we cannot model 3D objects. To express this, the specification of RO-Crate must be extended to represent multi-dimensional objects for places.

There are other layers in our Data Cube model that should be analyzed, the Data Acquisition and Product Information layer. The following table shows the metadata present in our Data Cube model and if they are present in RO-Crate.

The specification of the RELIANCE RO-Crate profile is published in the following link:

<https://reliance-eosc.github.io/reliance-ro-crate/>

A new vocabulary was created to model the new metadata introduced by the concept Data Cube. This metadata was analyzed in - D5.1 RO model adapted to EOSC -, section 3.3, Table 2. These new terms are identified with the **prefix rel**. New terms are published on:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/ro-terms/master/earth-science/vocabulary.ttl>

4 FAIR assessment of Research Objects

In the previous version of the document, we analyze the meaning of FAIR, a collection of tools used to assess the FAIRness of different research outputs and an initial design of a service used to assess the FAIRness of a Research Object.

In this new version of the document, we will describe the proposed approach to measure the FAIRness of a Research Object as well as the tool developed in RELIANCE to assess it.

4.1 Theoretical Framework

FAIR principles have been a subject of discussion in the last years. For instance, in [4], the authors propose a community-driven framework to assess the fairness in digital objects. This evaluation is based on: i) a collection of maturity indicators, ii) compliance tests, and iii) a module to apply those tests to digital resources. These indicators may be an starting point to define which tests are needed for each type of resource [5].

We cannot find in the literature, an specific related work about FAIRness in Research Objects. Nevertheless, there is an example of quality measurement in our project (quality checklist). This approach checks the inclusion of some metadata such as title, description, creator, publisher information, etc. Also, it checks if there are resources presents in the Research Object. As can be seen, it typically takes into account only the presence of general metadata. Checklists can also take into account metadata about the resources constituting the Research Object, and also verify if those resources are accessible. This, however, is just a subset of the FAIR principles. This is the reason why we decide to create a FAIR service.

In the first version of the deliverable, we identified that for assessing the FAIRness of a Research Object, we would need to assess each of the resources that compounds the Research Object. Also, the Research Object itself should be evaluated.

Each resource is evaluated against the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), and each principle is evaluated by a set of tests (which depend on the type of the resource and the FAIR assessment tool used). The final FAIRness score associated with a Research Object may vary depending on the percentage of passed by each resource and on the design decisions used to aggregate the FAIR scores.

We have defined two aggregation metrics in our framework to calculate the final FAIRness score of a Research Object. Note that the metrics are based on the tests defined for each principle and resource. Metrics do not change the tests executed, only how test results are dealt with in the aggregation formula. Our proposed metrics are:

- **Global metric:** calculated by formula (1). It represents the percentage of total passed tests. It doesn't take into account the principle to which a test belongs.
- **FAIR average metric:** calculated by formula (2). It represents the average of the passed tests ratios for each principle plus the ratio of passed tests used to evaluate the Research Object itself. Both metrics are agnostic to the kind of resource analyzed. The score they produce ranges from [0 - 100].

$$total_score_{global} = \frac{\#tests_passed}{\#tests} \tag{1}$$

$$total_score_{FAIR_average} = \frac{\sum_{i \in G} \frac{\#test_passed_i}{\#tests_i}}{\#G}, \tag{2}$$

where G represents the group of tests from the categories Findable (F), Accessible (A), Interoperable (I), Reusable (R) and Research Objects (RO).

4.2 FAIR assessment service

The architecture of the service (see Figure 4-1) follows the initial design defined in the previous document.

Figure 4-1 FAIROs Architecture

Our service has two main components:

- **Dispatcher.** This component analyzes the Research Object metadata file and detects the different resources of the Research Object (datasets, software and ontologies). Once the resources are analyzed, the information is sent to the specific tool.
- **Aggregator.** This component collects the results from the tests executed and aggregates the information to calculate a FAIR score for the Research Object. Tests depend of resource's

type and the FAIR principle. FAIROs is open source and available on GitHub (<https://github.com/oeg-upm/FAIR-Research-Object>)

In order to measure the FAIRness of Research Objects, FAIROs integrates existing tools to assess individual datasets, software and ontologies. These tools have been selected based on: i) their ability to assess the analyzed resources automatically, without human intervention, ii) their accessibility, iii) ease of use and iv) they implement metrics described in scientific publications.

For **datasets**, we have deployed in our server an instance of the application F-UJI. This application provides a REST service to assess the FAIRness of datasets based on 16 of the 17 metrics defined in the FAIRsFAIR Data Objects Assessment Metrics (<https://www.fairsfair.eu/fairsfair-data-object-assessment-metrics-request-comments>). The results of these tests are sent to the aggregator module.

For **ontologies**, we use the service provided by the Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!). This tool analyzes an ontology with several tests based on [6] [7] and returns a FAIRness score with an explanation of the results, categorized by each FAIR principle. The module dispatcher prepares the request and the response from FOOPS! is sent to the aggregator module.

Regarding **software** assessment, we have created a validator based on the principles identified in [8]. In order to extract metadata associated with a given code repository, we use the Software Metadata Extraction Frame work (SOMEF) [9], which analyzes repository documentation to retrieve the license, description, installation instructions, requirements, versions, citation text or provenance information (authors, creation date). These metadata fields are particularly relevant for reusability.

As shown in Figure 4-1, an additional component has been developed to execute SOMEF, run a set of tests to validate the extracted metadata and send the results to the aggregator component.

Table 1 summarizes the FAIR principles covered by the different components of our framework.

Table 1 FAIR principles coverage by the FAIR assessment tools used in FAIROs

Service	F1	F2	F3	F4	A1	A1.1	A1.2	A2	I1	I2	I3	R1	R1.1	R1.2	R1.3
F-UJI	X	X	X	X	X				X		X	X	X	X	X
SOMEF	X	X											X	X	
FOOPS	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	

The last component of the aggregator is in charge of evaluating the meta data of Research Objects themselves, by using RO-Crate specification and the ro-crate-py library. The tests we run to analyze the FAIR principles are detailed below:

- F1: We verify if the RO has a persistent identifier ['w3id.org', 'doi.org', 'purl.org', 'www.w3.org'].
- F2: We verify if the following minimum metadata ['author', 'license', 'description'] are present in the ro-crate.
- F3: We verify that the hasPart elements exists and are described in the RO.
- R1.1: We verify if there is at least one author, a datePublished and a citation in the root element.
- R1.2: We verify that all elements of the RO have the following fields: ['author', 'datePublished', 'citation']

FAIROs generates two outputs:

- A JSON file with the executed tests and the final/intermediate scores generated by a specific metric. The final score is calculated based on the metric selected. Each resource is analyzed based on the tests defined for each FAIR principle. Also, the different tests executed for each principle are described.
- A visual diagram explaining the scores and each test. The diagram is generated in the Graphviz format. An example can be seen in Figure 4-2.

The output JSON file format is composed by a list of components (resources of the Research Object), which defines the tests executed and the obtained scores. Inside each component, users can see the executed tests, and the explanation of their results.

```

1 {"principle_id": "F3",
2   "category_id": "Findable",
3   "title": "Metadata_clearly_and_explicitly_include_the_identifier_
   ↳ of_the_data_they_describe",
4   "description": "This_check_verifies_that_the_hasPart_elements_
   ↳ exists_and_are_describe_in_the_ro",
5   "total_passed_tests": 1,
6   "total_tests_run": 1,
7   "status": "ok",
8   "explanation": "All_element_identifiers_exists"
9 }

```

For each component, we include a summary of the tests categorized by principle. The final score calculated by the formula defined by the selected metric is included under the key overall_score.

```

1 "overall_score": {
2   "description": "The_score_is_calculated_by_adding_all_the_
   ↳ scores_of_the_different_components_together._All_passed_
   ↳ tests_and_all_total_tests_are_added_together_and_then_
   ↳ the_percentage_is_calculated",
3   "score": 37.5,
4   "total_sum": {
5     "total_passed_tests": 3,
6     "total_run_tests": 8
7   }
8 }

```

The output file format is the same for both of our proposed metrics. For additional information please refer to FAIROs publication [10].

Figure 4-2 Graphical representation of the RO assessment

4.3 Implementation

The FAIROs service is available via <https://fairos.linkeddata.es/api/>. The service exposes three methods:

- Jobs
 - POST inserts a new job in the service
 - GET return the status of a job in the service
- Login
 - POST login to the service
- Assessment
 - GET returns the assessment file of a Research Object

The API documentation is available at: <https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/esgg/FAIROs/1.0.0-oas3>, where it can also be tested.

4.4 Considerations

The use of different aggregation metrics, the FAIRness score of a RO can change significantly (even if scores are consistent with each other). This has two main implications: 1) scores may be used as a guideline to improve the quality of a Research Object, but should not act as a replacement for its quality; and 2) it is key to explain the aggregation method used to produce any Research Object FAIRness score. The objective of the scoring system should not be only to produce a ranking, but mainly to become a mechanism to improve the FAIRness of Research Objects.

Each type of resource (datasets, ontologies, etc.) has different number of tests, so the weight in the final score will depend on the proportion of resources defined in the Research Object. For example, imagine two Research Objects; one with 4 datasets and another with 6 datasets and 5 software packages. Since the number of tests to assess the FAIRness of software is much lower than the number of tests for datasets, the score of the first Research Object will likely be much better than the second, even when the second Research Object will be more comply to more FAIR principles, in percentage.

5 Community-driven quality assessment

RELIANCE aims to produce not only FAIR Research Objects, as described in the previous section, but also Research Objects of high quality according to what the research communities producing and reusing them consider relevant. Such quality assessment aims to provide, thus, an indication of the fitness of the Research Object in that particular community, typically by assessing a number of quality dimensions, such as accuracy, completeness, or availability.

To make such assessments, RELIANCE draw upon the idea of checklists, a well-established tool for ensuring safety, quality and consistency in complex operations, such as manufacturing or critical care [11, 12]. A checklist explicitly defines a list of requirements that must be fulfilled or assessed for a given task. Accordingly, RELIANCE is providing the mechanisms and tools to support the assessment of Research Objects quality following a community driven approach, where the needs and expectations of researchers in the community with respect to what makes research (re-)usable are translated and formalized into a set of quality checks.

To achieve this, RELIANCE leveraged and evolved existing Research Object quality assessment technology based on checklists (called RO-manager [13]), which check e.g., whether certain datasets are accessible, that appropriate and complete metadata facilitating its reuse is available or that a computational service is available. Such technology relies on the Minim ontology⁴ [14] (see Figure 5-1) to express quality requirements as RDF, and an assessment service to evaluate the conformance of target Research Object against a Minim checklist.

In RELIANCE, the checklist service was adapted and extended to interact efficiently with the latest ROHub (Research Object management) platform (see Section 5.1), to support RELIANCE metadata models and vocabularies (aligned with EOSC). Additionally, new checklists were created to reflect the RELIANCE community's needs (see Section 5.2 and 5.3).

Furthermore, as part of RELIANCE, the checklist service has been extended, during the last period, to enable an easy creation and customization of checklists to other community or group specific needs for the automated quality checking mechanisms (see Section 5.4). RELIANCE also provides means for monitoring the quality over time, generating alerts when there is a decay, so researchers can take appropriate measures (see Section 5.5).

Finally, to facilitate the assessment and generation of high-quality Research Objects, RELIANCE provides appropriate interfaces not only to assess but also to correct/improve the quality of the Research Object in a user-friendly manner (see Section 7.6.1), so that it remains available for reuse

⁴ <http://purl.org/minim/description>

and preservation. The availability of these mechanisms for the research community will encourage the growing adoption of reproducible practices in research management.

Figure 5-1 Minim data model

5.1 Checklist service Integration with ROHub

ROHub is the RELIANCE service providing the Research Object management functionalities. As part of RELIANCE, ROHub 2.0 was released and deployed. ROHub’s new architecture, as described in detail in Section 7, comprises a backend component exposing a RESTful API, an IAM component, (meta-) data and resource storage components and a set of user interfaces. Additionally, various external services are integrated with ROHub, including the checklist service that provides the Research Object (RO) quality assessment functionalities. The checklist service⁵ exposes a simple REST API to assess the RO quality comprising two GET methods:

- /trafficlight_json: return the evaluation result in JSON format
- /trafficlight_html: return an HTML representation of the result.

Both methods receive three parameters as input:

- Research Object, is the target RO to be evaluated
- Minim, is the particular checklist to be used for the evaluation. This checklist is an RDF document expressing the desired quality requirements to be checked based on the minim model (cf. Figure 5-1).

⁵ <https://sandbox.rohub.org/roevaluate2/evaluate/>

- Purpose, is the specific purpose in the checklist document to be used for the assessment. The purpose allows to group quality to conditions to check specific characteristics or features in a Research Object, e.g., completeness, accessibility, ready to release, etc. A checklist document may have multiple purposes, a purpose group multiple conditions, and a condition may be part of multiple purposes.

Internally, the checklist service contacts ROHub to retrieve the target RO's manifest and all the aggregated annotation bodies, which are used to build the full RO graph that is used as source for assessing the quality conditions. Each quality condition is then transformed into a SPARQL query that is assessed over the generated graph. Additionally, if the quality check requires assessing if an aggregated resource is accessible (e.g., an external service or data source), the checklist service retrieves from ROHub the resource location and checks if it can access it or not.

In order to integrate the checklist service with the latest ROHub API, both the checklist service⁶ and the ROHub required some adaptations and extensions, including the indexing of RO's manifest and annotation bodies in the ROHub's Elasticsearch index to speed up their access from the checklist service, an improved management of http sessions in the checklist service, and the addition of namespaces in checklist service to support the RELIANCE metadata model elements in the quality conditions, including:

- "sch": "https://schema.org/"
- "pav": "http://purl.org/pav/"
- "rel1", "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/earth-science#"

To access the checklist services functionalities, ROHub exposes them transparently to the user via its user interfaces. Hence, ROHub users do not need to change interface or use another tool to assess the quality of their Research Objects. In ROHub portal, the checklist functionality is available from the completeness tab of the Research Object. From this tab, the users can (re-)evaluate the Research Object completeness against the default or the provided checklist on demand. The default checklist is based on the RO type (see section below). The result of the evaluation is displayed in compact form in the overview tab, whereas detailed information is presented in the completeness tab, as described in Section 7.6.1. The checklist functionality is also available via the ROHub library, which is described in Section 7.8.

Furthermore, as part of RELIANCE we have adapted and extended the mkminimum tool (part of the checklist service code) in order to facilitate the customization of checklists to community needs (see Section 5.4).

5.2 RELIANCE checklists

Taking as starting point the work carried out in EVER-EST project regarding the characterization of Research Objects and their associated checklists [15], the requirements collected and distilled from the RELIANCE research communities include, among others, a simplified list of Research Object types and simplified checklists for each of these types (see Section 5 in D7.1 for further details). The types of Research Objects in RELIANCE are limited to:

- Bibliographic centric RO
- Data centric RO (including Data Cube)
- Executable RO (including Jupyter Notebooks)
- Basic RO

⁶ The RELIANCE adaptation of checklist service is available at <https://github.com/rapw3k/ro-manager>

Based on those types, the communities agreed on the following set of quality checks. The common checks are:

- RO has a title
- RO has a description
- RO has a creator
- RO has publisher information
- RO has a subject (research area)
- RO has a sketch
- RO has keywords
- The RO aggregates at least one resource
- The resources aggregated by the RO have a type
- Optionally, the RO may have authors defined for credits
- Optionally, the RO may have contributors defined for credits
- Optionally, the RO may have geolocation associated

Additionally, for a Bibliographic-centric RO:

- there is at least a resource in “biblio” folder

For a Data-centric RO:

- there is at least e resource in “raw data” folder
- there is at least a resource in “data” folder
- there is at least e resource in “metadata” folder

For an Executable RO:

- there is at least a resource in “input” folder
- there is at least a resource in “tool” folder
- there is at least a resource in “output” folder

Accordingly, we have generated four different checklists: one for the basic RO type⁷, which has the common checks, and one for each of the other types (bibliographic-centric⁸, data-centric⁹, and executable¹⁰) which include the common checks plus the type specific conditions. A snippet of the basic checklist implementation is provided in the table below.

⁷ The full checklist can be downloaded via: <https://box.psncl.pl/f/1e5c2d93d4/%3fraw=1>

⁸ <https://box.psncl.pl/f/9c399ea6d0/?raw=1>

⁹ <https://box.psncl.pl/f/f80f85131d/?raw=1>

¹⁰ <https://box.psncl.pl/f/1de488fc99/?raw=1>

Table 2 Basic RO checklist snippet

```

<minim:Model rdf:about="#experiment_complete_model">
  <rdfs:label>Complete experiment</rdfs:label>
  <rdfs:comment>
    This model defines information that must be satisfied by the target RO
    for the target RO to be considered a complete and fully-described experiment.
  </rdfs:comment>
  ## MUST
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_title"   />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_description" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_creator"  />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_publisher" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_subject"  />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_at_least_one_resource" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_sketch"   />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_keywords" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_resources_have_type" />
  ## OPTIONAL
  <minim:hasMayRequirement    rdf:resource="#RO_has_authors"  />
  <minim:hasMayRequirement    rdf:resource="#RO_has_contributors" />
  <minim:hasMayRequirement    rdf:resource="#RO_has_geolocation" />
</minim:Model>

<!-- RO title is present -->
<minim:Requirement rdf:about="#RO_has_title">
  <minim:isDerivedBy>
    <minim:ContentMatchRequirementRule>
      <minim:forall>
        ?ro rdf:type ro:ResearchObject, ore:Aggregation .
        FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?ro rdf:type ore:AggregatedResource }
        FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?ro rdf:type roterms:WorkflowRunBundle }
      </minim:forall>
      <minim:exists>
        ?ro dcterms:title|sch:title ?rotitle .
      </minim:exists>
      <minim:showpass>Research Object has title</minim:showpass>
      <minim:showfail>Research Object does not have title, , including <i>%<(ro)s </i></minim:showfail>
      You must add annotation: title (dcterms or schema vocabulary)</minim:showfail>
      <minim:derives rdf:resource="#RO_has_title" />
    </minim:ContentMatchRequirementRule>
  </minim:isDerivedBy>
  <minim:seq>001</minim:seq>
</minim:Requirement>

```

5.3 Sample checklist evaluation

For illustration purposes, below we provide the evaluation result of assessing the quality of one of the Research Objects from the supersites community using the basic checklist created based on RELIANCE requirements (for the purpose ready-to-release). The checklist API call is as follows:

https://sandbox.rohub.org/roevaluate2/evaluate/trafficlight_json?RO=https://w3id.org/ro-id/3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8&minim=https://box.psn.c.pl/f/1e5c2d93d4/%3fraw=1&purpose=ready-to-release

The result of call with a truncated description is presented in the table below:

Table 3 sample checklist evaluation result

```

{ "rouri": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8/"
, "roid": "3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8"
, "title": "Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM"
, "description": "The VSM (Volcano and Seismic source Modelling) tool is a Fortran code used to model ground deformation detected by the most common geodetic techniques (interferometric SAR, GPS, leveling and EDM - Electro-optical Distance Measuring)..Contact: Elisa Trasatti elisa.trasatti@ingv.it."
, "checklisturi": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#experiment_complete_model"
, "checklistpurpose": "ready-to-release"
, "checklisttarget": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8/"
, "checklisttargetid": "3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8"
, "checklisttargetlabel": "Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM"
, "evalresult": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#potentiallySatisfies"
, "evalresultlabel": "does not satisfy"
, "evalresultclass": ["fail", "must"]
, "checklistitems":
[ { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_title"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has title"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_description"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has description"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_creator"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has creator"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_publisher"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object does not have publisher. You must add annotation: publisher (dcterms or schema vocabulary)"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": false
, "itemclass": ["fail", "must"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_subject"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has subject"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_at_least_one_resource"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object aggregates at least one resource"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_sketch"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has sketch"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_keywords"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has keywords"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_resources_have_type"
, "itemlabel": "Aggregated resources have a type"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_authors"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object does not have author(s) (credit of its content). You should add annotation: authoredBy (pav vocabulary) "
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMayRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": false
, "itemclass": ["fail", "may"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_contributors"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object does not have contributor(s) (credit of its content). You should add annotation: contributedBy (pav vocabulary) "
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMayRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": false
, "itemclass": ["fail", "may"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psn.c.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_geolocation"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has geometry"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMayRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]}]]}

```

5.4 Checklist generation tool

The mkminim tool (part of the checklist service code) allows the generation of checklists from a CSV or a XLS file. As part of RELIANCE, the adapted and extended tool¹¹ allows researchers to create/customize their own checklists, without previous knowledge of minim data model or implementation details, and use them to assess their Research Objects' quality. Moreover, the use of the tool was simplified in RELIANCE, minimizing the number of required sections and fields and more importantly, allowing users to provide the requirement rules as simple text based on a controlled set of terms, instead of requiring them to provide them using SPARQL queries.

The checklist definition file requires the following sections:

- **Checklist definition:** This section associates a Minim Model with a purpose. When the checklist service is invoked, the RO, checklist and purpose are provided (see Section 5.3). The purpose is then matched against the available purposes in the checklists to select a Minim Model for evaluation. Example section:

Checklists:	Purpose	Model
	ready-to-release	#experiment_complete_model

- **Minim Model definition:** A Minim Model is an identified list of requirements to be satisfied, each with an associated requirement level ("MUST", "SHOULD" or "MAY"), and a sequence number that is used to order the individual requirement test results for presentation. The Model URI-reference identifies the defined Minim Model, and is used to associate a checklist definition (see above) with this entry. The requirement level (req-level) values indicate the level of importance attached to the corresponding requirement. The requirement identifier (req-id) values are URI references that identify the rules (see below) that are used to evaluate the corresponding requirement. Example section:

Model:	#experiment_complete_model	
Items:	Level	Rule
001	MUST	#RO_has_title
002	MUST	#RO_has_description

- **Requirement evaluation rule:** This section comprises a list of requirements evaluation rules definitions. There are different rule types, though all of them include the rule identifier (req_id), and diagnostic messages elements: Pass message (returned when the rule was satisfied), Fail message (when the rule was not satisfied), and No-match message (when the rule pre-condition was empty). Then, depending on the rule type, the rule has different format. The supported types/formats are:
 - Exists data rule
 - ForEach match Exists data
 - ForEach match Aggregates resource
 - ForEach match Accessible resource

¹¹ <https://github.com/rapw3k/ro-manager/blob/master/src/checklist/mkminim.md>

- Match cardinality rule
- Software environment test

The two most commonly used are the first four. The first two support a predefined set of terms (apart from SPARQL query patterns). For example “ForEach” can have as value “RO” or “Resource” to refer to target RO, or to each of the resources aggregated in the RO, respectively. Similarly “Exists” supports simple property names (e.g., title, description, creator, publisher, etc.) to verify that this property exists in the target RO or Resources (depending on “ForEach”) or predefined composite terms (aggregates_resource, aggregates_sketch, resource_type) to verify that at least one resource is aggregated, that at least one sketch is aggregated, or that resources have a type, respectively. Note that the property names are mapped into controlled vocabulary terms from schema.org, dublin core, or others, based on a predefined mapping of the most common ones, and to schema.org for any other. For full documentation please refer to the tool repository. Example rules:

Rule:	#RO_has_keywords	
	ForEach:	RO
	Exists:	keywords
	Pass:	Research Object has keywords
	Fail:	Research Object does not have keywords. You must add annotation: keywords. Keywords are separated by "\",\""
Rule:	#RO_resources_have_type	
	ForEach:	Resource
	Exists:	resource_type
	Pass:	Aggregated resources have a type
	Fail:	At least one aggregated resource does not have a type, including <i>%(aggregated_resource)s </i>. You must add annotation: type .
	None:	No resources are aggregated to check their type

5.5 Quality monitoring

Research Objects (ROs) are monitored through quality metrics such as completeness, stability, and reliability [16]. Completeness measures the extent to which a Research Object satisfies a number of requirements specified in a checklist, stability measures the degree to which the research object completeness remains unchanged, and reliability combines the previous metrics to provide a unique value indicating to what extent the Research Object is complete and how stable it has been historically. These values are calculated taking into consideration a checklist of quality requirements to be satisfied. The monitoring of ROs is carried out by the stability service, another added value being integrated with ROHub.

The stability service exposes a REST API and a notification feed, via the following methods:

- /exec-checklist: Runs a checklist evaluation on a RO and saves it in the database
 - **Method:** POST
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] AND Optional: checklist=[alphanumeric]
 - **Response codes:** Created (201), Bad Request (400), INTERNAL SERVER ERROR (500)
- /completeness: Gets the completeness quality metric for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: date=[yyyy-mm-dd]

- **Response:** [double]
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Not Found (404), Bad Request (400)
- **/stability:** Gets the stability quality metric for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** [double]
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Not Found (404), Bad Request (400)
- **/reliability:** Gets the reliability quality metric for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** [double]
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Not Found (404), Bad Request (400)
- **/quality-time-series:** Gets the time series of the calculated quality metrics for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:**

Table 4 Response from quality-time-series

```
[{
  "rouri": [alphanumeric],
  "roid": [alphanumeric],
  "evaldate": [date],
  "stabilitystartdate": [date],
  "stabilityenddate": [date],
  "completeness": [double],
  "stability": [double],
  "reliability": [double],
  "checklistitems": [
    {
      "itemuri": [alphanumeric],
      "itemlabel": [alphanumeric],
      "itemlevel": [alphanumeric],
      "itemsatisfied": [boolean]
    },
    ...
  ]
},
...]
```

- **/notifications:** Gets the Atom notifications of the calculated quality metrics changes for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** Atom feed
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Bad Request (400)

6 Evolution mechanisms

ROHub enables the management of versioning and evolution of Research Objects. The evolution or lifecycle of the Research Object (RO) comprises all the stages that the RO transitions from its conception until its conclusion. Different lifecycles scenarios were identified and analyzed in

previous projects (e.g., Wf4Ever, EVEREST). Based on that analysis the possible RO states were derived (see Figure 6-1) and implemented in ROHub:

- **Live ROs:** represent a work in progress. They are thus mutable as the content or state of their resources may change.
- **Snapshot ROs:** are intended as a record of past activity, ready to be disseminated as a whole. They are immutable, and reflect the state of the Live RO at a certain time.
- **Archived ROs:** represent the final stage of a RO where it has either reached a version that the author prescribes to be stable and meaningful and is appropriate for publication and long-term preservation, or it has been deprecated. They are therefore immutable, with no further changes or versions allowed.
- **Forked ROs:** throughout the Research Object lifecycle, new lines of work can be started at any point in time (e.g., to explore different hypothesis, test different configurations), either while the Research Object is alive by forking the Live RO at some point in time, or once the RO has reached a milestone/stable state by forking any of the RO snapshots or the RO archive.

Figure 6-1 Research Object Lifecycle States

An important challenge previously addressed was to support the assignment of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to Research Objects that are ready for publication during their lifecycle. This is particularly relevant for researchers, as it is the most typical mechanism used to cite research outputs, e.g., papers, datasets, etc. Hence, in order to allow citation of Research Objects, which can also count for the researcher academic score, it was important for ROHub to be able to generate a DOI for a Research Object. Accordingly, ROHub became a Datacite¹² DOI service provider.

¹² <https://datacite.org/>

The envisioned scenario is that once the researcher(s) consider that the LIVE Research Object on which they are working has reached some milestone and its content is worth of publication or sharing, for instance as a technical report for internal distribution or as scholar contribution to the research community, they can proceed to generate a SNAPSHOT, which as mentioned before is a copy at a certain point in time of a LIVE Research Object. SNAPSHOTS are good candidates to receive a DOI since, according to the definition, they are immutable and ready to be shared. It will be up to the scientist to decide if they want to assign a DOI when they generate a SNAPSHOT, and up to the Research Object management platform (ROHub) to verify that the Research Object fulfils the requirements, drawn from the Research Object checklist, to get it.

Similarly, when the researcher(s) consider the investigation to be final the Research Object is ARCHIVED. This is the state for Research Objects that have reached a high maturity degree such that its content is not going to be modified, and in such case also a good candidate for having a DOI, or that have been deprecated (e.g., research line stopped or found useless). Note that in a typical scenario, a LIVE Research Object gives rise to a number of SNAPSHOT Research Objects before producing an ARCHIVED Research Object.

Furthermore, throughout the Research Object lifecycle, new lines of work can be started at any point in time (e.g., to explore different hypothesis, test different configurations), either while the Research Object is alive by forking the LIVE RO at some point in time, or once the RO has reached a milestone/stable state by forking an RO SNAPSHOT or an RO ARCHIVE (see Figure 6-1). The FORK(ed) RO is a subtype of LIVE RO, and thus it works in the same way, i.e., A SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE can be generated from a FORK RO, and thus assigned a DOI.

As part of RELIANCE, the lifecycle was further extended in order to leverage and reuse existing EOSC services. The goal was to allow the publication of shareable Research Objects (i.e., SNAPSHOTS/ARCHIVES) in general/popular EOSC repositories like Zenodo or B2Share, which could contribute to their dissemination, increasing their findability and potential reuse (i.e., their FAIRness). The Research Object is published in those repositories in the form of an RO-crate, which is the current standard method to capture and describe the Research Object using structured metadata¹³ (see D5.1). Moreover, RO-crate has been agreed as the exchange format of Research Objects with other people in the community, including representatives of OpenAire (Zenodo).

Hence, in order to support the previous scenario, ROHub provides now the user with different options when generating a SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE:

- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE with a DOI provided by ROHub and publish it in Zenodo and/or B2Share
- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE and publish it in Zenodo and/or B2share, which will generate a DOI for it
- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE with a DOI provided by ROHub without publishing it somewhere else
- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE without DOI or publishing it anywhere else.

In the latest ROHub release, the evolution mechanisms were extended with the integration of B2Drop, another EOSC service, which can be selected as the default storage location for the internal resources added and aggregated by the Research Object during its lifecycle (see Section 7). Additionally, a preliminary analysis and testing was carried out to support additional operations during the lifecycle, particularly to enable the creation of pull requests from Research Object forks and their merging to their original (forked) Research Object. As this is not a critical feature, its

¹³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.1/introduction.html>

implementation is planned for the next big ROHub release. Instead, during the last period additional efforts were made for the integration of ROHub with other EOSC services (beyond the original plan).

The latest features to the Research Object lifecycle management are depicted in Figure 6-2. ROHub interfaces to evolution features are described in Section 7.

Figure 6-2 Research Object Lifecycle State with RELIANCE features

7 Integration and access

ROHub [17, 18] is the main service in RELIANCE providing the Research Object management functionalities. It is a holistic solution for the storage, lifecycle management and preservation of scientific investigations, campaigns and operational processes via Research Objects. As part of RELIANCE, a new and enhanced ROHub¹⁴ was released. ROHub integrates multiple services, including RO added value services (e.g., coming from WP3 and WP4), as well as EOSC services that are being leveraged and reused. This enables, for example, the automatic enrichment of Research Objects with metadata extracted from the aggregated unstructured textual content, or the aggregation of Data Cubes, along with detailed metadata, in the Research Object to access large structured datasets (like Copernicus data). Additionally, ROHub provides the user interfaces to access all the latest Research Objects functionalities, including a reference Web Portal and a Python library that can be used, for instance, via Jupyter Notebooks. A high-level view of the new ROHub architecture, including the underlying technologies, is depicted in Figure 7-1.

As depicted in the figure, ROHub’s architecture comprises a backend component, an IAM component, (meta-) data and resource storage components and a set of user interfaces. Additionally, various external services are integrated with ROHub, including the checklist service and

¹⁴ <https://reliance.rohub.org/>

quality monitoring tool (see Section 5), the FAIRness assessment service (see Section 4), the text mining and enrichment services (WP3), the PDF service, and multiple EOSC services, including ADAM platform for EO data discovery and access through data cubes (WP4). In the following sections we describe each of these components in detail.

Figure 7-1 ROHub high-level architecture

7.1 ROHub backend

The ROHub backend is the main service exposing all the Research Object management functionalities through a comprehensive RESTful API. The service has been implemented using Django (Python-based) web framework¹⁵, Django REST framework for building the API¹⁶, and Varnish Cache as HTTP accelerator¹⁷. In RELIANCE there are two instances of ROHub backend: the production instance has deployed the latest stable version of the service and stores all the real Research Objects, while the development instance has deployed the ongoing additions/updates that are being tested before becoming a stable version and stores only test Research Objects.

The service is available at:

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/> (production). (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psnec.pl/api/> (development)

¹⁵ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

¹⁷ <https://varnish-cache.org/>

Figure 7-2 ROHub backend service API entry point

The service can be tested via Swagger at:

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/swagger/> (production) (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psnr.pl/api/swagger/> (development)

Figure 7-3 ROHub backend service API Swagger interface

A detailed documentation is available via Redoc.

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/redoc/> (production) (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psnec.pl/api/redoc/> (development)

Figure 7-4 ROHub backend service redoc documentation

7.2 ROHub IAM

The ROHub Identity and Access Management (IAM) is based on Keycloak technology. It allows users to authenticate to ROHub and enables the single sign-on across different RELIANCE services. The most important feature of ROHub IAM is that is integrated with EOSC AAI. In particular it allows the user to authenticate through the EGI check-in service. There are two instances of ROHub IAM: the production instance integrated with production EGI check-in and having the official set of ROHub users, and the development instance integrated with development EGI check-in and having test users.

The service is available at:

- <https://login.rohub.org/> (production)
- <https://keycloak-dev.apps.paas-dev.psnec.pl/auth/realms/rohub/account/> (development)

Figure 7-5 below depicts the ROHub login page to authenticate through the selected Keycloak instance. From there, the user can authenticate via the EGI check-in service or by providing directly his email and password.

If the user selects to login with EGI check-in, then (s)he can use any of the identity providers supported by EGI check-in service (see Figure 7-6), such as its academic institution or one of the social account providers (e.g., orcid, google, Facebook, GitHub, LinkedIn, etc.). After selecting the academic/social identity provider, the user should follow the normal process of the provider to authenticate, providing its username/email and their password. If the user chooses to provide his email and password directly on ROHub login page, (s)he should provide its password in ROHub (not their academic/social account password).

Figure 7-5 ROHub login page

Figure 7-6 EGI check-in login page

Once the user is logged in, (s)he will be able to see and/or edit his/her user account settings in ROHub The Figure 7-7 below depicts the entry point to the user account settings, which includes the following sections:

- Account information, which includes all the user account fields that can be saved in ROHub, i.e., salutation, first name, last name, affiliation, description, areas of interest, user token in Zenodo, user token in B2Share, Orcid, Resource Storage, B2Drop user and password, and ADAM platform key. The Resource Storage field allows the user to select the storage to be used for the physical resources aggregated in his/her Research Objects. This can be the default ROHub storage (S3 store) or the user’s B2Drop space (see Section 7.4). The storage selected is applied for newly created Research Objects (since the change of storage), i.e., previously created Research Objects keep the storage selected when it was originally created.

Figure 7-7 ROHub account settings

- Change password: This section enables the user to change the password of his/her account in ROHub. This password is independent of the EGI check-in password.
- Authenticator: ROHub AIM allows the user to save the device as a second level authentication. This is done through third party authentication applications (e.g., FreeOTP, Google Authenticator). The application scans the barcode provided in the user’s account and generates an OTP which along with the name of the device can be saved.
- Federated identities: This section shows the user identity in EGI check-in, if any, which is essentially the username of the user in EGI.
- Sessions: Shows the current sessions for the user account. The session record consists of information like the user IP address, the start and end time of the session etc.

- Applications: This section shows the IAM application clients that this user is able to use to authenticate in ROHub, along with the roles and permissions associated to this account. The client used is generally transparent to the user, as it is set internally by the application itself (e.g., ROHub portal, ROHub python library, Enrichment service, etc.).
- Log: This section shows all the available activity log for the user account in ROHub, including the date of the event, type of the event (i.e., login), IP source, application client used, and any additional information like the username and authentication method used.

7.3 *Meta(data) storage and index*

ROHub uses different storage systems to store metadata and indexes. In particular, it uses:

- Virtuoso triplestore¹⁸: stores all the Research Object metadata and annotations as RDF triples represented according the RO core model and vocabularies¹⁹. Accordingly, the RO is described by a manifest including the RO metadata along with information about the resources aggregated, which can be resources (internal or external), folders and annotations about the RO and those resources. Each annotation has an associated body (also aggregated), which includes the actual metadata (e.g., RO title, RO description, type of resource, etc.). Similarly, each folder has an associated manifest with the list of resources it contains. This model provides a lot of flexibility and scalability in terms of the metadata that can be associated to the RO and its aggregated resources. In Virtuoso, each RO has one named graph for its manifest and one for each annotation body aggregated. Note that although internally ROHub uses the RO model to represent and describe ROs, it uses RO-crate as the default exchange format for Research Objects, e.g., to publish them in Zenodo/B2Share. Hence, ROHub internally maps the RO model to the RO-crate specification.
- PostgreSQL²⁰: stores information about the internal functioning of ROHub. This is the default storage for Django model objects, and thus it includes information of the Research Objects (a subset of the RDF metadata), about the resources (a subset of the RDF metadata), about the users (a sub set of Keycloak information), etc. Additionally, PostgreSQL stores some technical data (not needed in the triplestore) that is necessary for ROHub execution like information whether a Research Object was cloned (e.g., as part of a snapshot/archive/fork generation), information about readers and editors of a Research Object, their quality information, likes/dislikes, ratings and comments associated.
- Elasticsearch²¹: stores all the indexes in ROHub that are used to speed up the access to commonly used information, such as Research Objects (with a subset of the RDF metadata), users (a subset of the RDF metadata), activities, organizations, enrichment metadata, ADAM collections and products, communities, ROHub statistics, RO's manifests and annotation bodies. Additionally, the indexes include information imported from external systems like Zenodo regarding existing open source licenses in addition to the custom ones added by the users, funders, grants, and vocabularies.

Each ROHub instance has its own metadata storages and indexes. Hence, currently there are two instances for each of those services, one for ROHub production and one for ROHub development.

7.4 *Resources storage*

A Research Object can aggregate both internal and external resources. For the latter, the RO aggregates the location (e.g., URL) where the physical resource can be accessed, while for the former the resource is physically uploaded to ROHub, and stored in the selected storage. Currently

¹⁸ <http://vos.openlinksw.com/owiki/wiki/VOS>

¹⁹ <https://www.researchobject.org/initiative/research-object-model/>

²⁰ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

²¹ <https://www.elastic.co/>

ROHub supports two types of storages: i) S3 compatible object storages, such as Minio²², Ceph²³, or the Amazon S3 Simple Storage Service²⁴; ii) B2Drop EOSC service²⁵. The user can select the storage type from his/her account settings (see Section 7.2), as depicted below.

Figure 7-8 Selection of storage type from ROHub user account settings

When selecting B2Drop, the users need to provide their B2Drop credentials also via the account settings. These credentials can be obtained from the B2Drop Web portal navigating to the security section from the user settings (“create new app password”)²⁶, as depicted in Figure 7-9 below.

Figure 7-9 B2Drop user settings

When B2Drop is selected as default storage, ROHub creates the root folder “Rohub/ros” in the user’s B2Drop space. Then, for each newly created RO by the user, which aggregates physical resources, a folder with the RO id is created inside that root folder, as depicted in Figure 7-10 below. When using B2Drop, the users need to take into account the space available in their own B2Drop account. The Research Objects’ internal resources will use this space, and If his/her B2Drop account has no more space available, then (s)he will not be able to aggregate physical resources in his/her Research Objects. One additional feature, currently under testing, is the synchronization of the RO folder in B2Drop with ROHub, i.e., resources added into the RO folder in B2Drop via any interface (e.g., B2Drop Web portal) will be automatically aggregated in the RO.

²² <https://min.io/>

²³ <https://ceph.io/en/>

²⁴ https://aws.amazon.com/s3/?did=ft_card&trk=ft_card

²⁵ <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/>

²⁶ <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/settings/user/security>

Figure 7-10 B2Drop folder structure created by ROHub

Each ROHub instance has its own default resource storage. ROHub development instance uses a Minio service deployed at PSNC, while ROHub production currently uses Amazon S3 (soon to be moved into PSNC’s new S3 infrastructure).

7.5 ROHub middleware services

ROHub application is deployed in a PaaS (Platform as a Service) environment, and relies on different middleware services enabling communication and execution of jobs. These include:

- Celery²⁷: an asynchronous task queue that is based on distributed message passing. This service is used by ROHub to carry out time consuming operations asynchronously like importing Research Objects, or creating snapshots, archives and forks. Celery also includes the celery beat, which is a scheduler that kicks off tasks at regular intervals that are executed by available worker nodes in the cluster. Examples of these tasks include: refreshing the index of Research Objects, activities and statistics, calculating size of internal resources, and the execution of enrichment and stability services. Celery requires a solution to send and receive messages; usually this comes in the form of a separate service called a message broker. In the case of ROHub, this broker is RabbitMQ.
- RabbitMQ²⁸: the message broker used by Celery in ROHub.

7.6 External services

ROHub integrates and reuses different external services. These include:

- RO added value services
 - Checklist service
 - Quality monitoring service
 - FAIROs service
 - Text mining services (EOSC services)
 - PDF service

²⁷ <https://docs.celeryproject.org/en/stable/index.html>

²⁸ <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

- ADAM Platform (EOSC service)
- Other EOSC services
 - EGI check-in
 - Zenodo
 - B2Share
 - B2Drop
 - EGI Notebook
 - EGI Binder
 - OpenAire Research Graph

In the following we briefly describe each of them:

7.6.1 Checklist service

As described in Section 5, this service functionality is available from both ROHub interfaces (Portal – see Section 7.7 and Python library – see Section 7.8). In ROHub Portal, this functionality can be invoked from the completeness tab (depicted in the Figure 7-11 below), by clicking the “Update” button. The result of the assessment is then displayed in detail, where each condition has a status icon: green check icon if the condition was satisfied, red cross icon if a MUST condition was not satisfied, and yellow hyphen icon if a SHOULD/MAY condition was not satisfied. Moreover, for those conditions not satisfied, a “Fix” button will appear next to it, if the user has permissions to write the RO. This button takes the user to the edition mode to fix those problems. To facilitate this process, the completeness score appears in edition mode and the conditions not satisfied can be seen under the “completeness suggestions” collapsible section (as depicted in Figure 7-12).

Figure 7-11 Checklist service interface in ROHub

Figure 7-12 Completeness information in Research Object edition mode in ROHub

Finally, the completeness score appears in a compact section in overview tab in the form of a (partially) filled bar, with the percentage score, as depicted in .

Figure 7-13 Completeness score in overview tab in ROHub Portal

The checklist used by the service to assess the completeness is by default dependent on the Research Object type. There are four pre-configured checklists: one for the basic RO type, one for bibliographic ROs, one for data-centric ROs, and one for executable ROs. For any other RO type, the basic checklist is used by default. However, the user is also able to specify his own/custom checklist to be used to assess the Research Object completeness. This functionality is available from the “provide your own checklist here” link (see Figure 7-12), which opens a small dialog box to enter the URL to the checklist and the purpose/target to be used. Hence, users will be able to generate their own checklists, as described in Section 5.4, and then use them to assess the completeness of their Research Objects.

From the ROHub library, a simplified checklist functionality is available via the completeness method, described below:

completeness(verbose=False)

Function that shows completeness score and details for the research object.

Parameters: **verbose** (*bool*) – if True full details will be displayed, otherwise only score with basic metadata, optional.

Returns: completeness information

Return type: dict

Figure 7-14 Completeness method in ROHub python library

7.6.2 Quality monitoring service

As described in Section 5, this service is being integrated in ROHub, and thus it will be available via the ROHub portal and Python library (in a simplified way). The ROHub portal will show a graphical representation of the Research Object quality history along with the quality values (completeness, stability, reliability), while the library will show only the quality values. The implementation is currently under testing. The integration of this service was delayed in favor of integrating other EOSC services, originally not planned, which were deemed to have a higher priority, according to our users and research communities.

7.6.3 Text mining and enrichment services

The text mining and enrichment service is described in detail in deliverable D3.3 submitted alongside this document. These include production-ready services and extended analytic services. The former refers to the enrichment service (the main service), a search service and a recommendation service. ROHub is fully integrated with the latest release of the enrichment service, and thus its functionality is available both from the ROHub portal and the Python library. The service is executed automatically by ROHub for new/updated Research Objects at certain periods of time (every few hours by default), but the user can force the (re-)execution of the service on demand.

From ROHub portal, the user is able to execute the service on demand and visualize the annotations generated from the Research Object overview tab. The enrichment component shows the annotations in different color depending on the type of annotation, as depicted in Figure 7-15. To call the service on demand, the user needs to be logged in and have write permissions over the Research Object, and then (s)he needs to click on the refresh icon at the right top corner of this component (see Figure 7-16).

Figure 7-15 Enrichment annotations displayed in ROHub portal

Figure 7-16 Invoking enrichment service on demand from ROHub portal

From ROHub python library, the enrich service can be called on demand using the enrich method described below

enrich()

Functions for applying enrichment to the research object.

Warning

The enrichment process can take a while. We recommend waiting a few minutes and then checking a job status manually by running a prompted command.

Returns: API response

Return type: dict

Figure 7-17 Enrich method in ROHub python library

Regarding the other production services, ROHub is also integrating the recommendation service (the search service is not needed as ROHub has its own indexes). This recommender functionality is available in the ROHub portal from the collapsible similar RO section in the Research Object overview tab, where users can display a list of Research Objects similar to the selected one, as depicted in Figure 7-18 below.

LOCATION: ▼

CONTENT ▼

ACTIVITY View All ↗

📄 ANNOTATION UPDATED → RO
 on 23.09.2022 (12:26) by service-account-enrichment

📄 ANNOTATION ADDED → RO
 on 23.09.2022 (11:38) by The Environmental Data Science Comm...

📄 ANNOTATION UPDATED → RO
 on 23.09.2022 (11:26) by service-account-enrichment

LIFE CYCLE CHART View All ↗

RO CREATED → RO **Exploring Land Cover Data (Impact Observatory) (Jupyter Notebook) published in the Environmental Data Science book**
 on 22.09.2022 (00:54) by The Environmental Data Science Comm...

SIMILAR ROS ^

PUBLIC
MANUAL
LIVE
EXECUTABLE RESEARCH OBJECT
ENVIRONMENTAL DATA SCIENCE BOOK COMMUNITY
JUPYTER NOTEBOOK

Created 24 July 2022 (20:43)

CLIMATOLOGY, ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH

Concatenating a gridded rainfall reanalysis dataset into a time series (Jupyter Notebook) published in the Environmental Data Science book

Timothy Lam, Marlene Kretschmer, Samantha Adams, Rachel Prudden, Elena Saggioro

Resources 10

Figure 7-18 Similar ROs section in Research Object overview tab

Regarding the new extended analytic services, which have been just released at the same time of this document, will be integrated in the next few months, after an initial validation/testing of communities and their feedback with respect of expectations in ROHub.

7.6.4 FAIROs service

As described in Section 4, FAIROs service measures the FAIRness of Research Objects, by calculating the FAIRness of individual aggregated resources, including the Research Object itself, and then aggregating those results to calculate the over FAIR score. The service has been recently deployed, and it is currently being integrated in ROHub. The service functionality will be available via the ROHub portal and python library in a similar way as the checklist service functionalities, i.e., in the portal the overall score will be displayed in the overview tab of the Research Object, and there will be a dedicated tab to show details of the FAIRness evaluation.

7.6.5 PDF service

The PDF service is a simple service that generates a paper style representation of the Research Object in PDF format. The service is available both from the ROHub portal and the python library, and it provides to scientists the possibility to download the Research Object as a PDF (as depicted in the Figure 7-19 below). From the library, this functionality is not yet available.

DOI: 10.24424/783F-5T97

Created: 07.04.2022 (15:12), last modified: 12.04.2022 (07:29)

PUBLIC MANUAL SNAPSHOT SOFTWARE-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT

APPLIED SCIENCES EARTH OBSERVATION EARTH SCIENCES

Volcanic and Seismic source Modelling (VSM). The Python toolkit for modelling geodetic data

Elisa Trasatti

Volcanic and Seismic source Modelling (VSM) is an open source Python tool to model ground deformation detected by satellite and terrestrial geodetic techniques. The VSM tool allows the user to choose one or more geometrical sources as forward model among sphere, spheroid, ellipsoid, fault, and sill. It supports multiple datasets from most satellite and terrestrial geodetic techniques: interferometric SAR, GNSS, levelling, Electro-optical Distance Measuring, tiltmeters and strainmeters. Two sampling algorithms are available, one is a global optimization algorithm based on the Voronoi cells and the...

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Figure 7-19 PDF service functionality from ROHub portal

A partial view of the generated PDF is provided in the Figure 7-20 below.

Volcanic and Seismic source Modelling (VSM). The Python toolkit for modelling geodetic data

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Abstract—Volcanic and Seismic source Modelling (VSM) is an open source Python tool to model ground deformation detected by satellite and terrestrial geodetic techniques. The VSM tool allows the user to choose one or more geometrical sources as forward model among sphere, spheroid, ellipsoid, fault, and sill. It supports multiple datasets from most satellite and terrestrial geodetic techniques: interferometric SAR, GNSS, levelling, Electro-optical Distance Measuring, tiltmeters and strainmeters. Two sampling algorithms are available, one is a global optimization algorithm based on the Voronoi cells and the second follows a probabilistic approach to parameters estimation based on the Bayes theorem. VSM can be executed as Python script, in Jupyter Notebook environments or by its Graphical User Interface. Version 1.0 April 2022. For any inquires, please write to elisa.trasatti@ingv.it

Keywords—geodetic data inversion, open science, deformation modelling, SAR data, seismic cycle, volcanic activity

I. INTRODUCTION

This document provides a paper-style view of the Research Object (RO) *Volcanic and Seismic source Modelling (VSM)*. The Python toolkit for modelling geodetic data¹ which is a *SNAPSHOT*.

Fig. 1. Research Object Sketch 1

The RO research area is: *Applied sciences Earth observation Earth sciences* and is of type ².

An overview of this RO is depicted in Figure 1.

This PDF file has been generated on 2022-10-05 19:07:40

II. RO DATA

The resources encapsulated by the RO are summarized in table I

The folders encapsulated by the RO are summarized in table II

TABLE I
RESEARCH OBJECT RESOURCES

Name	Type	Creation time
³ VSM tests in GitHub using InS...	Example Run	2022-04-07 13:59:08
⁴ M 7.1 Van Earthquake (Turkey)...	Research Object	2022-04-07 19:22:56
⁵ Santorini (Greece) 2011-2012 ...	Research Object	2022-04-07 14:32:55
⁶ Nyiragongo volcano (DR Congo)...	Research Object	2022-04-07 13:26:39
⁷ Campi Flegrei Caldera (Italy)...	Research Object	2022-04-07 13:25:22
VSM logo	Image	2022-04-07 13:23:18
figure2.png	Sketch	2022-04-07 13:15:18
License of use of VSM	Bibliographic Resource	2022-04-07 14:03:09
⁸ VSM code in GitHub	Python Script	2022-04-07 13:56:11

TABLE II
RESEARCH OBJECT FOLDERS

Name	Parent	Creation time
Examples	None	2022-04-07 13:24:23
Figures	None	2022-04-07 13:22:25
VSM_src	None	2022-04-07 13:24:11

A. Resources description:

VSM tests in GitHub using InSAR and GNSS data at Campi Flegrei caldera (Italy): Tests of VSM in GitHub using InSAR and GNSS data at Campi Flegrei caldera (Italy). M 7.1 Van Earthquake (Turkey) 2011: Application of VSM to the M7.1 Van Earthquake (Turkey) of 2011. Santorini (Greece) 2011-2012 unrest: Modelling of the 2011-2012 unrest at Santorini (Greece).. Nyiragongo volcano (DR Congo) 22 May 2021 eruption : Data modelling related to the 2021 eruption at Nyiragongo volcano (DR Congo) using VSM. Campi Flegrei

³https://github.com/EliTras/VSM_test

⁴<https://doi.org/10.24424/dxfh-x940>

Figure 7-20 Partial view of a Research Object in PDF format

7.6.6 ADAM platform

The ADAM platform (described in deliverable D4.2, D4.4) exposes EO Data Cubes collections and products, which can be described and aggregated in the Research Object. ADAM has been integrated in ROHub, so that collections/products can be easily aggregated in Research Objects from the ROHub portal and python library. During the aggregation, the collection/product metadata from ADAM is added automatically as annotations of the resource created in the Research Object, using the RELIANCE ro-crate profile and vocabulary described in Section 3.

From ROHub portal in the resources section of the edition mode, user can click on the add data cube resource icon, and in the dialog box that appears, (s)he is able to select from the dropdown list (or using autocomplete) the data cube collection, and optionally the data cube product (inside that

collection), and then add optionally other basic metadata (title, description, license, keywords), as depicted in Figure 7-21.

Figure 7-21 Aggregation of Data Cube collections/products from ROHub portal

Data cubes collection/products aggregated in the Research Object can be opened directly in ADAM platform to visualize them on the 3D globe. When a user clicks on a data cube collection from ROHub, it will be opened in ADAM. And when the user clicks on a data cube product, (s)he can choose to go to the physical resource (download the geoTiff file by default), or open it in ADAM platform, as depicted in Figure 7-22. Figure 7-23 shows the visualization of a data product in ADAM platform.

Figure 7-22 Opening a Data Cube product from ROHub portal

Figure 7-23 Visualization of a Data Cube product in ADAM platform

From the python library, users can aggregate Data Cubes collections/products via the `aggregate_datacube` method, described below:

```
aggregate_datacube(dataset_id, product_id=None, product_media_type=None)
```

Function that aggregates datacube from adam platform to a research object.

Parameters:

- **dataset_id** (*str*) – dataset identifier
- **product_id** (*str*) – product identifier, optional
- **product_media_type** – media type, has to be one of: image/tiff, image/png or application/xml, optional

Returns: response from api

Return type: dict

Figure 7-24 Aggregate data cube method in ROHub python library

7.6.7 EGI check-in

The integration of EGI check-in in ROHub is described in Section 7.2.

7.6.8 Zenodo

As described in Section 6, users are able to publish snapshots/archives of Research Objects in Zenodo and/or B2Share. This functionality is available from both the portal and library as part of the evolution mechanisms.

From ROHub portal, the user can generate a snapshot/archive from the source Research Object overview page using the third button in the toolbox (as depicted in the Figure 7-25 below).

Created: 27.05.2022 (23:36), last modified: 16.09.2022 (13:32) ☆ 0.00 / 5 0 0

PUBLIC **MANUAL** **LIVE** EXECUTABLE RESEARCH OBJECT

EARTH SCIENCES
NO2 (April 2019, 2020, 2021) in Spain Jupyter notebook demonstrating the usage of CAMS European air quality analysis from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring with RELIANCE services
 Anne Fouilloux

Contributed by Jean laquinta, Simone Mantovani
 Published by University of Oslo, Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration

This Research Object demonstrates how to use CAMS European air quality analysis from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring with RELIANCE services and compute monthly map of NO2 over a given geographical area, here Spain

10 Downloads **4** Views
[Hide more details](#)

Resources	4
Annotations	27
Events	41
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	216.00 KB

AGENTS
 admin NordicESMHub
 Creator

COMPLETENESS 83%

TOOLBOX

SHARE
 Evolution
 Fork
 Snapshot
 Archive

CITE AS

CONTENT

Figure 7-25 Evolution mechanisms from ROHub portal

Selecting any of the evolution options (fork, snapshot, archive) will open the RO creation wizard, customized to the state selected. In the case of snapshot/archive, the wizard gives the possibility to generate a DOI or provide an existing DOI, and/or to publish it in Zenodo/B2Share (as depicted in the Figure 7-26 below).

Basic information | People & organizations | Tags | Sketches gallery | Resources | Related locations | License & Funding | Advanced metadata

Completeness: 83%

Last updated: 29.05.2022 (23:12) [Update](#)

Completeness suggestions [Show more](#)

Title *

Description *

Publication services none b2share zenodo

Create DOI not applicable add existing doi generate doi

[Snapshot & Exit](#) [Reset form](#) [Snapshot & Go to overview](#)

Figure 7-26 Creating a snapshot from a Research Object from ROHub portal

From the library, the user can use the method `snapshot` or `archive` from the current Research Object. Below is the description of the `snapshot` method.

snapshot(title=None, description=None, create_doi=None, external_doi=None, publication_services=None)

Function that creates research object's snapshot.

See also

`list_valid_publication_services()`

Note

if one chooses to use doi it can be provided in two ways: 1) through setting `create_doi` to `True`, then doi will be generated for you 2) through passing your doi using `external_doi` parameter `create_doi = True` and `external_doi` are mutually exclusive, therefore they can't be used simultaneously!

Note

if on chooses to use publications services the result will be loaded as an RO-crate!

Warning

user needs to make sure that he has service credentials associated with his profile for the publication services that he would like to use! If that is not the case, warning will be shown and the ros will not be published as intended!

- Parameters:**
- **title** (*str*) – snapshot title, optional
 - **description** (*str*) – snapshot description, optional
 - **create_doi** (*bool*) – doi is created if `True`, `False` otherwise, optional, `False` is the default
 - **external_doi** (*str*) – existing doi value that will be associated with the snapshot, optional
 - **publication_services** (*list*) – services where the snapshot should be published into

Returns: snapshot identifier

Return type: `str`

Figure 7-27 Snapshot method in ROHub python library

For illustration, the Figure 7-28 below shows a Research Object²⁹ published in Zenodo³⁰.

²⁹ <https://w3id.org/ro-id/a369aaf0-06f7-441a-9a18-3b79b9d45f8e>

Figure 7-28 Research Object published in Zenodo

7.6.9 B2Share

The integration with B2Share works in the same way as the one with Zenodo that was explained in the previous section.

For illustration, the Figure 7-29 below shows a Research Object³¹ published in B2Share³².

³⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/6510214#.Yz33tOxBw-Q>

³¹ <https://w3id.org/ro-id/c737f695-6715-4916-8bef-8fc0ce879760>

³² <https://b2share.eudat.eu/records/3c82435c669b49fcaa5541b465e055fa>

Figure 7-29 Research Object published in B2Share

7.6.10 B2Drop

The integration of B2Drop in ROHub is described in Section 7.4.

7.6.11 EGI Notebooks

ROHub integrates EGI Notebooks service, enabling users to open and execute their Jupyter Notebooks in EGI Notebooks directly from ROHub portal. In order to use this functionality: i) the user needs to have an account with access to EGI Notebooks service³³; ii) the user needs also to have an account and be logged in ROHub; iii) and the resource to be reproduced must have type “Jupyter Notebook”. When the user clicks on such resource in ROHub portal, independently if it’s an internal or external resource, s(he) can choose to go to the resource itself (download the notebook) or to open it in EGI Notebook, as depicted in the below. If the user opens the resource in EGI Notebook, the service will be launched and the user will be able to execute it as depicted in the below.

Figure 7-30 Opening a Jupyter Notebook in EGI Notebook from ROHub portal

³³ <https://notebooks.egi.eu/>

Figure 7-31 Executing in EGI Notebook the Jupyter Notebook selected in ROHub

7.6.12 EGI Binder

As one step further from previous section, ROHub also integrates EGI Binder service, which enables users not only to open and execute their Jupyter Notebooks directly from ROHub portal, but also to reproduce the full computing environment by pre-loading all the libraries and dependencies required to execute the notebook. Binder supports further the best practices in reproducible data science by utilizing community-developed standards for reproducibility. In order to use this functionality: i) the user needs to have an account with access to EGI Binder service³⁴; ii) the user needs also to have an account and be logged in ROHub; iii) the resource to be reproduced must have type “Jupyter Notebook”; iv) the Research Object must aggregate at least one configuration file named requirements.txt or environment.yml; v) the notebook is connected to the configuration file via the relation “softwareRequirements” (from schema.org). This relation can be established by selecting the notebook in the resources section of the Research Object edition mode, and then creating the relation under the show all annotations, as depicted in Figure 7-32 below.

³⁴ <https://binder.notebooks.egi.eu/>

Figure 7-32 Establishing a relation between two resources in ROHub portal

When the user clicks on such resource in ROHub portal, independently if it's an internal or external resource, s(he) can choose to go to the resource itself (download the notebook) or to open it in EGI Binder, as depicted in the Figure 7-33 below. If the user opens the resource in EGI Binder, the service will be launched, all the dependencies will be imported to recreate the computing environment, as depicted in the Figure 7-34 below, and then the user will be able to execute the notebook.

Figure 7-33 Opening a Jupyter Notebook in EGI Binder from ROHub portal

Starting repository: rohub/notebooks/link_da4d3c23-c1b9-3cc1-9361-ce91de445e95

Read our [advice for speeding up your Binder launch.](#)

```
Build logs
Step 45/48 : USER $(NB_USER)
--> Running in c7857e766f6c
Removing intermediate container c7857e766f6c
--> 35694fbd7f46
Step 46/48 : COPY /repo2docker-entrypoint /usr/local/bin/repo2docker-entrypoint
--> 96e4a3db64da
Step 47/48 : ENTRYPOINT ["/usr/local/bin/repo2docker-entrypoint"]
--> Running in a31da5d85bf2
Removing intermediate container a31da5d85bf2
--> d9a1eeb8956c
Step 48/48 : CMD ["jupyter", "notebook", "--ip", "0.0.0.0"]
--> Running in 64f21f313efc
Removing intermediate container 64f21f313efc
--> 2c5f9c7d935b
["aux": {"ID": "sha256:2c5f9c7d935b3a83d18db43edb432a50674e4f2923799f0595f1fced2f22d3a"}]Successfully built 2c5f9c7d935b
Successfully tagged docker-notebooks.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu/binder-dev-rohub-2dnotebooks-1900d1:3ea2e15e1ff12626f8ba31f0c5796ff25afc7d98
Pushing image
Pushing image
Pushing image
Pushing image
```

Figure 7-34 Recreating computing environment in EGI Binder from the ROHub resources

7.6.13 OpenAire Research Graph

ROHub is also integrated with the OpenAire Research Graph³⁵. Following the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers 4.0³⁶ that support the EC Open Access requirements, ROHub exposes its Research Objects collection to the OpenAIRE infrastructure, including funding information, where applicable, and the list of their resources aggregated. Additionally, ROHub exposes Jupyter Notebooks and Data Cubes, as especially relevant collections, with their connections to Research Objects. This required to implement and configure an OAI-PMH v2.0³⁷ endpoint in ROHub³⁸, producing XML metadata for OpenAIRE harvesting (see a partial record of a Research Object in XML in Figure 7-35).

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" ?>
<record>
  <header>
    <identifier>https://w3id.org/ro-id-dev/000e0d8-762d-454b-9449-0f7c1bf642c</identifier>
    <timestamp>2022-10-06T00:27:59Z</timestamp>
    <setSpec>rohub_data</setSpec>
    <setSpec>ro-create_data</setSpec>
  </header>
  <metadata>
    <oaicomponent xmlns="http://schema.datacite.org/oai/oai-1.0/" xsi:schemaLocation="http://schema.datacite.org/oai/oai-1.0/ http://schema.datacite.org/oai/oai-1.0/oai.xsd">
      <isReferenceQuality>true</isReferenceQuality>
      <schemaVersion>4.0</schemaVersion>
      <datacentreSymbol>PSNC.ROHUB</datacentreSymbol>
    </oaicomponent>
    <payload>
      <resource xmlns="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4" xsi:schemaLocation="http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-2.1/metadata.xsd">
        <contributors>
          <contributor contributorType="Researcher">
            <contributorName>Generation Service</contributorName>
          </contributor>
        </contributors>
        <creators>
          <creatorName>CNR-ISMAR</creatorName>
        </creators>
        <dates>
          <date dateType="Issued">2018-06-20T11:36:00Z</date>
        </dates>
        <dc:description>
          <dc:description descriptionType="Abstract">The main objective of recent international legislative measures and policies concerning marine ecosystems is to ensure sustainable environmental management to maintain a good status for marine waters, habitats and resources, with the ultimate target of achieving an integrated ecosystem-based approach to management. Because bioinvasions pose significant threats to marine ecosystems and the goods and services these provide, non-indigenous species (NIS) are included in the more recent legislative documents. A major challenge for the scientific community is to translate the principles of the legislative directives into a realistic, integrated ecosystem-based approach and at the same time provide stakeholders with best practices for managing NIS. The aim of this paper, prepared by members of the Working Group on Introductions and Transfers of Marine Organisms (WGITMO) of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), is to provide guidance for the application of NIS related management in the European Union Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Ten recommendations, including NIS identification, standardization of sampling and data, indicators, propagate pressure and management issues are considered in this paper. While most of these suggestions were developed to improve the implementation of the MSFD, several may be more widely applicable. (C) 2013 Elsevier Ltd. All rights reserved.</dc:description>
        </dc:description>
        <identifier identifierType="w3id">https://w3id.org/ro-id-dev/000e0d8-762d-454b-9449-0f7c1bf642c</identifier>
        <dc:publisher>Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center</dc:publisher>
        <dc:publicationYear>2018</dc:publicationYear>
        <relatedIdentifiers>
          <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="w3id" relationType="HasPart">https://w3id.org/ro-id-dev/000e0d8-762d-454b-9449-0f7c1bf642c/resources/3c298938-4c5c-415a-8690-ae45c57047</relatedIdentifier>
          <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="w3id" relationType="HasPart">https://w3id.org/ro-id-dev/000e0d8-762d-454b-9449-0f7c1bf642c/resources/019e501a-0834-44e6-aae8-bb31b937329f</relatedIdentifier>
        </relatedIdentifiers>
      </resource>
    </payload>
  </metadata>
</record>
```

Figure 7-35 Research Object metadata record in XML format from ROHub OAI-PMH endpoint

- 35 <https://graph.openaire.eu/>
- 36 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1299203>
- 37 <http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>
- 38 <http://api.rohub.org/api/oai2d/>

As a result, Research Objects, and these other special resources, are now discoverable via the OpenAire/EOSC explore portal³⁹, as depicted in Figure 7-36. Currently, this integration is available via the beta instance of OpenAire Research Graph, but it will be moved into production by the end of October 2022. The target frequency for OpenAire harvesting is daily, i.e., in an incremental basis, so that only new records will be retrieved each day.

Figure 7-36 OpenAire/EOSC explore showing Research Objects harvested

7.7 ROHub Portal

The ROHub portal is a Web client application providing a comprehensive user interface for the management and preservation of Research Objects (ROs). A new portal was created as part of RELIANCE project, taking into account all the feedback received over the years about the previous portal, and using a more modern stack of technologies which can be easily maintained and extended. In particular, the new ROHub portal was developed using React⁴⁰, JavaScript library for building user interfaces based on UI components. In RELIANCE there are two instances of ROHub portal: the production instance has deployed the latest stable version of the portal and uses the production instance of ROHub backend and IAM, while the development instance has deployed the ongoing additions/updates that are being tested before moving them to a stable version and uses the development instance of ROHub backend and IAM.

The portal is available at:

- <https://reliance.rohub.org/> (production). (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psnec.pl/> (development)

A full user guide for the ROHub portal is available at <https://reliance-eosc.github.io/rohub-portal-documentation/> (live document).

³⁹ <https://beta.explore.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁰ <https://reactjs.org/>

7.8 ROHub Python Library

RELIANCE also produced an ROHub Python library, providing a user-friendly API for working with Research Objects. The Python API works on top of the ROHub backed REST API, wrapping and abstracting the REST methods in user friendly API methods. One of the main goals for this library was to enable users to work with Research Objects directly from Jupyter Notebooks, which is the main working and computing environment in RELIANCE.

The Package is distributed through Python Package Index (PyPI), and so it can be installed easily by typing: ***pip install rohub***

The full documentation of the ROHub library API, including a quick-start guide, various user-oriented tutorials and changelogs is available at: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/index.html. A snippet of the documentation showing the method to create a Research Object is shown below.

```
rohub.ros_create(title, research_areas, description=None, access_mode=None, ros_type=None, use_template=False, owner=None, editors=None, readers=None, creation_mode=None)
```

Function that creates new Research Object in the API and instantiates a Python object that can be reused.

i See also

```
list_valid_research_areas()
list_valid_access_modes()
list_valid_ros_types()
list_valid_templates()
list_valid_creation_modes()
```

i Note

The newly created research object will return a Python object that has its own set of methods and attributes. You may want to assign it to a variable to make it easy to work with. For example: `my_ros = ros_create(**your set of params)`

Parameters:

- **title** (*str*) – title of your research object
- **research_areas** (*list*) – research areas associated with your research object
- **description** (*str*) – description of your research object, optional
- **access_mode** (*str*) – research object's access mode, optional
- **ros_type** (*str*) – research object's type, optional
- **use_template** (*bool*) – if True appropriate template for ro type will be used, optional
- **owner** (*str*) – research object's owner, optional
- **editors** (*list*) – research object's editors, optional
- **readers** (*list*) – research object's readers, optional
- **creation_mode** (*str*) – research object's creation mode, optional

Returns: newly created research object

Return type: [ResearchObject](#)

Figure 7-37 Research Object create method in ROHub python library

The library is distributed as open source code under an MIT license and is available from PSNC code repository⁴¹.

A demo Jupyter Notebook showcasing (many of) the library method is available at: <https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks/blob/main/ROHub-library-prod-demo.ipynb> (see Figure 7-38). This and other sample Jupyter Notebooks are available in GitHub project sample-notebooks (of RELIANCE-EOSC organization)⁴².

```

Import library

In [ ]:
import rohub

Authenticate

In [ ]:
rohub_user = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-user").read().rstrip()
rohub_pwd = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-pwd").read().rstrip()
rohub.login(username=rohub_user, password=rohub_pwd)
#rohub_client_id = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-client_id").read().rstrip()
#rohub_client_secret = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-client_secret").read().rstrip()
#rohub.login(client_id=rohub_client_id, client_secret=rohub_client_secret)

RO methods

Create new RO

In [ ]:
ro_title="8th December - Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service Data Cube Research Object"
ro_research_areas=["Earth sciences"]
ro_description="This Research Object demonstrate how to compute monthly map of PM10 over your country"
ro_ros_type="Data-centric Research Object"
ro_ros_template="Data Centric Research Object folders structure"

ro = rohub.ros_create(title=ro_title, research_areas=ro_research_areas, description=ro_description, ros_type=ro_ros_type, template=ro_ros_

Find ROs

In [ ]:
rohub.ros_find(search="December")

List my ROs

In [ ]:
myros=rohub.list_my_ros()
myros[0:10]

```

Figure 7-38 Snippet of the demo Jupyter Notebook showcasing ROHub library

8 Conclusions

This document describes the status of the second major release of the tools and services for Research Objects (ROs) management, resulting from the WP5 tasks, including the services for FAIR assessment and quality assessment of Research Objects, the adaptations of Research Objects evolution to EOSC scenarios, the integration of services from WP3 and WP4, and other EOSC services, and the current state of the user interfaces. Although this is the last document describing the status of these services, they will continue to evolve/improve throughout the rest of the project based on the user's feedback and updates from the EOSC ecosystem in general. One of the major achievements of this work has been the integration of ROHub with multiple services, including RO added value services, but most importantly with many other EOSC services. There are over 13 services (if we count the individual text mining services) integrated or finalizing the integration with ROHub, which is actually beyond the original plan of the project. Some integrations were delayed in favor of other services with higher priority to the users, and are therefore still being finalized/tested. The FAIROs service, recently released, is under integration still, given the short time since its deployment. Also the new extended analytic services have been released recently (at the same moment of this document), and thus they will require still some testing/validation from users, and

⁴¹ <https://git.man.poznan.pl/stash/projects/ROHUB/repos/rohub-api/browse?at=refs%2Fheads%2Fmaster>

⁴² <https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks/>

then it is planned to integrate them as well in ROHub. As the project RELIANCE has been officially extended, such task will still be possible as part of the project.

Regarding the FAIR assessment of Research Objects, the FAIROs service has been recently released, and it is currently being integrated with ROHub.

Regarding the quality assessment, the services for RELIANCE have been deployed, by extending and adapting existing tools. The checklist service is fully integrated in ROHub, and a tool facilitating the creation and customization of checklists has been released. The integration of the quality monitoring service is still under testing.

Regarding the evolution mechanisms, the integrations to Zenodo and B2share have been finalized to publish Research Object snapshots/archives in these platforms from ROHub. Also, other evolution operations have been analyzed, e.g., merging and/or pull requests, but given the low priority given by our communities, they are not being implemented yet in favor of other services.

The document describes the final architecture of the ROHub platform, and all the services it integrates, including Research Object added value services, ADAM platform and other EOSC services. Most of these integrations are finalized and in production, e.g., checklist, enrichment, PDF, ADAM, EGI check-in, Zenodo, B2Share, B2Drop, EGI Notebooks, EGI Binder, OpenAire RG. But some are still being improved or under testing, e.g., B2Drop synchronization, quality monitoring, or are still to be done, i.e., the new FAIROs and the extended text mining analytics services. Finally, the document describes the user interfaces of ROHub providing the links to the documentation and user guides.

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